

Seeing Accessibility: A Vision–Language Approach to Disability-Related Spatial Inequality from Street View Imagery

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GISRUK 2026

Summary

This study introduces a Visual Accessibility Score (VAS) that uses street view imagery and vision–language models to capture micro-scale environmental conditions affecting disabled mobility. Focusing on Liverpool, UK, pedestrian environments were assessed for enabling features and barriers at sidewalks and crossings, aggregated from street level to neighbourhood scale. Results reveal substantial spatial inequalities in accessibility that only partially align with conventional deprivation measures and disability prevalence. Areas with high disability prevalence often coincide with poorer visual accessibility, though notable mismatches exist. The findings demonstrate the added analytical and policy value of incorporating image-derived environmental accessibility into assessments of spatial vulnerability and inclusive urban design.

KEYWORDS: Street View, Accessibility, Equality, Disability, Computer Vision.

1 Introduction

Barriers to accessibility continue to limit disabled people’s engagement with services, amenities, and everyday activities, largely owing to the design and condition of the built environment rather than individual impairments alone (Oliver et al., 2012). Features such as uneven pavements, obstructions, narrow sidewalks, and inaccessible crossings restrict mobility and participation, reinforcing inequalities and undermining well-being (Gleeson, 1999). Despite policy commitments including SDG 11 (United Nations, 2025) and the UK Equality Act 2010 (UK Government, 2010), these fine-grained, place-specific barriers remain difficult to systematically measure across cities.

While a substantial literature on disability and social exclusion exists, dominant spatial measures of disadvantage focus primarily on socioeconomic characteristics or realised outcomes, such as employment, health, or service use (Schwanen et al., 2015). The English Index of Multiple Deprivation

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(IMD) is one of such examples (McLennan et al., 2025). While informative, these indicators capture the consequences of exclusion rather than the environmental conditions that produce it. As a result, accessibility constraints and obstacles may remain invisible where disabled residents adapt, withdraw, or self-select in response to barriers (Gleeson, 1999; Kwan, 2012). Moreover, areas with similar deprivation profiles, as measured by deprivation indexes, may present markedly different mobility conditions for disabled residents.

Recent advances in Street View Imagery (SVI) and Vision–Language Models (VLMs) offer new opportunities to address this gap. Models such as CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining) enable visual scenes to be assessed against natural-language descriptions, supporting scalable detection of pedestrian accessibility features (Radford et al., 2021). While SVI has been widely used to study urban form and environmental quality (Biljecki and Ito, 2021), applications explicitly targeting disability-relevant micro-scale barriers remain limited.

In this work, we propose a Visual Accessibility Score (VAS) derived from SVI using open-source VLMs to capture micro-scale environmental conditions relevant to disabled mobility. Using Liverpool (UK) as a case study area, we examine how street-level image-derived accessibility measures are associated with disability prevalence and conventional deprivation measures, and how such associations reveal priority areas for potential street design intervention. Rather than replacing existing indices, we demonstrate the analytical and policy-oriented value of incorporating environmental accessibility into assessments of spatial vulnerability for disabled people, motivating the development of disability-focused measures that better reflect people’s lived experience.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study area and spatial units

Liverpool was selected as a study area due to its well-documented socioeconomic inequalities, diverse urban morphology, and relatively high prevalence of disability, with clusters of high deprivation and health burden in distinct parts of the city (Morrissey, 2015). Analysis is conducted at the Lower-layer Super Output Area (LSOA) level to ensure compatibility with IMD data and disability prevalence statistics.

2.2 Street view imagery sampling and pre-processing

The pedestrian street network of Liverpool was obtained using OSMnx (Boeing, 2025). Then, Google Street View panoramic images were sampled across the network every 100 metres and at intersections (Figure 1). To ensure temporal relevance, only images dated from 2020 onwards were used for accessibility scoring. Figure 2 shows the distribution of the sampled images across Liverpool. The 360° panoramas were cropped and transformed into planar, or perspective, projection at four directions, i.e., 0°, 90°, 180°, 270°, to reduce distortion of features (Figure 1), using the Python package ZenSVI (Ito et al., 2025). For images located at or near the intersection (within 20 m, to capture the functional and visual extent of crossing-related features which often extend beyond the junction centroid), all four directions were preserved, while for images located in the middle of

Figure 1: Workflow for deriving Visual Accessibility Scores (VAS) from street-level imagery and integrating them with area-level indicators.

Figure 2: Locations of all sampled Google Street View images across the street network at intersections (white) and sidewalks (blue).

Table 1: Visual accessibility prompt categories used for CLIP-based scoring. Each prompt represents a distinct, visually observable accessibility concept and is grouped by functional relevance and spatial context.

Context	Type	Example prompts
Sidewalk	Enabling	wide sidewalk; smooth pavement surface; continuous sidewalk; clear and unobstructed sidewalk
Sidewalk	Barrier	narrow sidewalk; broken or uneven pavement; sidewalk blocked by street furniture; parked cars obstructing the sidewalk
Crossing	Enabling	pedestrian crossing with clear markings; curb ramp at a crossing; tactile paving at a crossing; unobstructed crossing area; accessible pedestrian signals
Crossing	Barrier	raised curb at a crossing; steps at a street crossing; uneven surface at a crossing; street furniture blocking a crossing

the street, only the directions along the street axis (i.e., 0° and 180°) were preserved to prioritise pedestrian-relevant perspectives. No personally identifiable information was extracted.

2.3 Visual accessibility scoring

A set of natural-language prompts was formulated as observable environmental features relevant to disabled mobility, curated based on the systematic review by Georgescu et al. (2024). The prompts were grouped into enabling conditions and barriers, and further distinguished by *sidewalk*- and *crossing*-related relevance (Table 1) (Figure 1). Each accessibility concept, which denotes a single, concrete accessibility feature that is visually observable in street-level imagery (e.g., a curb ramp at a crossing), was represented by a small ensemble of paraphrased prompts describing the same feature in different ways (e.g., “a curb ramp at a pedestrian crossing”, “a sloped curb at a street crossing”, “a dropped curb for pedestrians”, “a wheelchair-accessible curb ramp”, “a smooth ramp connecting sidewalk and road”). Prompt-level scores were then aggregated to obtain a robust concept-level estimate, reducing sensitivity to linguistic variation.

For each image i and prompt p , CLIP was used to compute the cosine similarity between the image embedding \mathbf{v}_i and the text embedding \mathbf{t}_p :

$$s_{ip} = \frac{\mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{t}_p}{\|\mathbf{v}_i\| \|\mathbf{t}_p\|}. \quad (1)$$

For a given concept c with prompt ensemble \mathcal{P}_c , similarities were aggregated by averaging:

$$S_{ic} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{P}_c|} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_c} s_{ip}. \quad (2)$$

To ensure comparability across concepts, scores were min-max normalised to the interval $[0, 1]$ across all images:

$$\tilde{S}_{ic} = \frac{S_{ic} - \min(S_c)}{\max(S_c) - \min(S_c)}. \quad (3)$$

Min-max normalisation was preferred over z-score standardisation because CLIP similarity distributions are non-Gaussian and concept-dependent, and bounding scores to $[0, 1]$ facilitates stable aggregation across heterogeneous visual features. For each image, normalised concept scores were aggregated according to both functional type (enabling vs. barrier) and spatial relevance (sidewalk vs. crossing).

Let $\mathcal{CE}^{(d)}$ denote the set of enabling concepts associated with spatial dimension d , and $\mathcal{CB}^{(d)}$ denote the corresponding set of barrier concepts, where $d \in \text{sidewalk, crossing}$ (Table 1). Enabling and barrier scores for image i were then computed as the mean of the normalised concept scores within each set:

$$E_i^{(d)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{CE}^{(d)}|} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{CE}^{(d)}} \tilde{S}_{ic}, \quad (4)$$

$$B_i^{(d)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{CB}^{(d)}|} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{CB}^{(d)}} \tilde{S}_{ic}. \quad (5)$$

This aggregation treats all concepts within a group equally and yields separate enabling and barrier estimates for each spatial dimension. Thereafter, a dimension-specific Visual Accessibility Score was defined as:

$$VAS_i^{(d)} = E_i^{(d)} - B_i^{(d)}. \quad (6)$$

Finally, images were assigned context weights based on street-network topology. For images located at intersections, sidewalk- and crossing-related scores were combined as:

$$VAS_i = w_i^{\text{sidewalk}} VAS_i^{\text{sidewalk}} + w_i^{\text{crossing}} VAS_i^{\text{crossing}}, \quad (7)$$

where the weights satisfy $w_i^{\text{sidewalk}} + w_i^{\text{crossing}} = 1$. By construction, the Visual Accessibility Score is bounded between -1 (barriers dominate) and $+1$ (enabling features dominate), with values near zero indicating mixed or neutral accessibility conditions.

In this study, intersection images were assigned a weight of $w_i^{\text{sidewalk}} = 0.3$ and $w_i^{\text{crossing}} = 0.7$, based on a normative assumption that, at intersections, accessibility conditions at crossings play a more critical role in determining safe and independent pedestrian mobility for disabled users than adjacent sidewalk conditions. Images located away from intersections were assigned full weight to sidewalk-related accessibility ($w_i^{\text{sidewalk}} = 1$) and zero weight to crossing-related dimensions ($w_i^{\text{crossing}} = 0$). We acknowledge that this simplification does not capture mid-block crossings and the weighting is

more normative than empirical. Future steps will involve refined context classification and sensitivity analyses on different weighting strategies.

Image-level scores were aggregated to their corresponding street segments by averaging all images snapped to each segment (Figure 1). Segment scores were subsequently aggregated to Lower-layer Super Output Areas (LSOAs) (Figure 1). Bivariate choropleth maps were plotted between VAS and IMD rankings, and between VAS and disability prevalence (percentage of disabled population living in each LSOA, based on the 2021 UK Census), across LSOAs, to expose spatial patterns of environmental and socio-economical disadvantages and to identify priority zones for future intervention (Figure 1). The methodology pipeline is openly available at <https://github.com/Junguin/seeing-accessibility-gisruk>.

3 Results

Figure 3: Visual Accessibility Scores (VAS) averaged at street level (A) and LSOA level (B).

Preliminary spatial visualisations suggest substantial within-city heterogeneity in accessibility conditions. At the street level, positive accessibility conditions were observed around the city centre and along major roads, while negative conditions were more commonly observed at minor streets (Fig-

ure 3A). When aggregated to the LSOA level (Figure 3B), these variations are smoothed, producing clearer spatial clusters of relatively higher and lower accessibility. Areas with lower average VAS tend to concentrate in inner urban neighbourhoods, while higher VAS values are more prevalent in peripheral areas, suggesting systematic spatial inequalities in the quality of pedestrian environments. The comparison also illustrates how aggregation masks within-area disparities, underscoring the value of street-level analysis for identifying specific locations where accessibility interventions may be most needed.

Figure 4: Bivariate choropleth maps showing spatial patterns between VAS and IMD ranks (A), and between VAS and disability prevalence (B) across LSOAs.

Bivariate mapping shows that many neighbourhoods with higher deprivation (lower IMD rank) coincide with lower VAS (Figure 4A), indicating that visually poorer pedestrian environments are more common in socio-economically disadvantaged areas. However, this pattern is not universal: pockets of relatively high accessibility exist within deprived areas, and some less deprived neighbourhoods still exhibit low VAS (Figure 4A). This spatial mismatch suggests that accessibility inequalities are shaped not only by socio-economic status but also by local urban form, historical development, and targeted infrastructure investment.

Meanwhile, areas with a greater share of disabled residents frequently coincide with lower accessi-

Figure 5: Distribution of most deprived (lowest IMD ranks), medium, and least deprived (highest IMD ranks) across LSOAs, with highlighted zones showing locations with the greatest (cyan) and least (white) gaps between accessibility provision and needs, respectively.

bility conditions (Figure 4B), implying a compounding disadvantage where populations with higher accessibility needs are more likely to live in less accessible street environments. Nonetheless, there are also neighbourhoods with high disability prevalence and moderate-to-high VAS (Figure 4B), indicating that better-designed environments can exist even where needs are high.

Priority areas were identified as LSOAs with the lowest VAS and highest disability prevalence (corresponding to the white zones in Figure 4B), which largely coincide with the most deprived regions (Figure 5). On the other hand, areas with the highest VAS and lowest disability prevalence (corresponding to the dark purple zones in Figure 4B) coincide largely with the least deprived areas (Figure 5). This shows that while the IMD is a useful policy tool to reveal priority regions in need of intervention, the inclusion of physical environmental parameters can improve the precision of such identification.

4 Conclusions and Future Steps

This paper demonstrates the feasibility of using VLMs and SVI to capture fine-grained, disability-relevant accessibility features that are not represented in conventional deprivation indices. The proposed VAS reveals spatial patterns that diverge from both IMD rankings and disability prevalence, underscoring the importance of incorporating physical environmental conditions to reveal priority zones for potential accessibility intervention to promote inclusive mobility. While providing valuable insights, the existing approach has several limitations: lack of interpretability and lack of attention to other environmental constraints such as terrain incline and the role of public transport in shaping mobility. Future steps will extend the scope to larger urban areas and incorporate broader dimensions of accessibility, including transport connectivity and access to public transport. Vision–language captioning models such as BLIP (Bootstrapped Language-Image Pretraining) will be integrated to enhance the interpretability of visual scores, alongside sensitivity analyses of prompt design, weighting schemes, and aggregation choices. In addition, non-image-based environmental attributes, such as slope, will be incorporated to better capture mobility constraints that are not directly observable in street-level imagery. Building on these advances, the approach will be developed into a disability-focused spatial vulnerability index that combines environmental accessibility with demographic and contextual factors to better inform targeted policy interventions.

5 Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) [ES/Y001796/1] through the North West Social Science Doctoral Training Partnership (NWSSDTP). The authors gratefully acknowledge this support.

6 Biography

All contributing authors should include a biography of no more than 50 words each outlining their career stage and research interests.

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References

- Biljecki, F. & Ito, K. (2021). Street view imagery in urban analytics and gis: A review. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 215, 104217, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2021.104217>.
- Boeing, G. (2025). Modeling and Analyzing Urban Networks and Amenities With OSMnx. *Geographical Analysis*, 57(4), 567–577, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gean.70009>. eprint: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/gean.70009>.
- Georgescu, A.-I., Allahbakhshi, H., & Weibel, R. (2024). The impact of microscale street elements on active transport of mobility-restricted individuals: A systematic review. *Journal of Transport & Health*, 38, 101842, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2024.101842>.
- Gleeson, B. (1999). *Geographies of Disability*. Routledge.
- Ito, K., et al. (2025). ZenSVI: An open-source software for the integrated acquisition, processing and analysis of street view imagery towards scalable urban science. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 119, 102283, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2025.102283> <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0198971525000365>.
- Kwan, M.-P. (2012). The uncertain geographic context problem. *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, 102(5), 958–968, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00045608.2012.687349>.
- McLennan, D., et al. (2025). *The English indices of deprivation 2025: Technical report*. Technical report, Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government.

- Morrissey, K. (2015). Exploring Spatial Variability in the Relationship between Long Term Limiting Illness and Area Level Deprivation at the City Level Using Geographically Weighted Regression. *AIMS public health*, 2(3), 426–440, <https://doi.org/10.3934/publichealth.2015.3.426>.
- Oliver, M., Sapey, B., & Thomas, P. (2012). *Social work with disabled people*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Radford, A., et al. (2021). Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision. *CoRR*, abs/2103.00020 <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.00020>.
- Schwanen, T., Lucas, K., Akyelken, N., Cisternas Solsona, D., Carrasco, J.-A., & Neutens, T. (2015). Rethinking the links between social exclusion and transport disadvantage through the lens of social capital. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 74, 123–135, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2015.02.012>.
- UK Government (2010). Equality act 2010. Accessed: 2026-01-03 <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2010/15/contents>.
- United Nations (2025). Sustainable development goals. Accessed: 2026-01-03 <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>.